

MAPWORMS

Mimicking Adaptation
and Plasticity in
WORMS

D1.3 FAIR-COMPLIANT DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The current report refers to the Deliverable 1.3 (D1.3), entitled “FAIR-compliant Data Management Plan” of the MAPWORMS project. The MAPWORMS Data Management Plan (DMP) aims to define the management steps and protocols to inform and guide the researchers involved in the project, in properly managing their data and software. The MAPWORMS Team acknowledges the importance of good data management of research data and the creation of a sound Data Management Plan (DMP) in anticipation of planned research activities. Following the Horizon 2020 FAIR Data Management Plan (DMP) Template ^[1], the MAPWORMS DMP includes information about the handling, collection, process, and generation of research data, the applied methodologies and standards, the procedures for sharing and making the data open access and the curation and preservation of the data.

This is the first version of the MAPWORMS DMP, which should be considered a living document that can be revised and will be matured based on the progress achieved through the lifecycle of the project.

1 INTRODUCTION

MAPWORMS project aims to design robots that are inspired by simplified forms of marine Annelida, able to perform tasks in response to environmental stimuli, thus adapting to the working environment with a shape-morphing strategy with unique features in terms of powering and eco-friendliness. Specifically, this project, intends to: 1) study the adaptation and plasticity of the marine Annelids body; 2) develop a mathematical model of Annelida plasticity and adaptation to the environment; 3) develop smart soft materials embodying responsiveness, shape morphing, and self-healing capabilities, based on DNA components; 4) develop bio-inspired modular shape morphing robots across the scale.

This deliverable presents the MAPWORMS DMP which should be considered a living document that can be revised in accordance with the project achievements. As it is stated in the Description of Action (DoA) and specifically in Task 1.3, this DMP is a reference document for the Consortium and it will outline how the research data collected or generated within the project activities will be handled during the project and will remain in force after the end of the project.

Since data gathering and curation are key factors, a Data Manager (DM) was appointed for the Data Management Plan (DMP) handling during the MAPWORMS kick-off meeting, on the 13th of May 2022, in Pisa (Italy). Figure 1 presents the organizational structure of the MAPWORMS DMP. The DM defines the framework of data handling to inform and guide all participating partners in properly managing their data (and software). The DM will be in contact with all partners - individually and as a group - throughout the project life in order to discuss and solve any possible difficulties in data sharing and publishing. In addition, the DM will work closely with the Innovation Manager (IM) and the Innovation Management

Board (IMB) for the appropriate handling of data and in particular of those related to the project results patenting.

Figure 1 Organizational structure of the MAPWORMS Data Management Plan

This document is the first version of the MAPWORMS DMP and is related to all six Work Packages and in particular: WP1 Project coordination, dissemination, and communication, WP2 Ecological, taxonomical and morphological studies for selected species of marine Annelida, WP3 Annelid shape-morphing modelling, WP4 Smart stimuli-responsive hydrogels, WP5 Morphing robots across scales and WP6 Robots testing towards application case studies and exploitation activities.

1.1 ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION

Grant Agreement number: 101046846

Project title: Mimicking Adaptation and Plasticity in WORMS

Project acronym: MAPWORMS

Call: HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01

Topic: HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01-01

Type of action: HORIZON-EIC

Service: EISMEA/E/01 Project

Starting date: May 01, 2022

Project duration: 48 months

Data Management Plan Responsible: HCMR

1.2 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN SCHEDULE

As already mentioned, this DMP is a living document which will be revised following the project progress. Several Data Management Team meetings among the different partners will be organised throughout the project duration, where the data delivery and standardisations will be discussed and finalised. The timeline of the evolution of the DMP is illustrated in Figure 2. This is the first version of the DMP which outlines how the research data collected or generated within the project activities will be handled during the project and will remain in force after the end of the project.

An updated version of the DMP (D1.7) will be created during the M30 in the framework of the second reporting period. The first results of several tasks will have been completed (e.g., D2.2, D2.3, D3.1, D3.2, D4.1, D5.1, D5.2) which will be used in order to update the DMP accordingly.

The final version of the DMP (D1.11) will be accomplished at the end of the project (M48) in the framework of the third reporting period. The tasks will have been completed and the DMP will be updated according to the project's final results.

Figure 2 DMP timeline

2 DATA SUMMARY

MAPWORMS data will be used to develop bio-inspired robots able to perform tasks in response to environmental stimuli. Specifically, the data generated and collected from WP2 will be related to annelid taxonomy, behavior, and ecology in order to provide the

biological background for WPs 3, 4 and 5. Furthermore, data derived from the WP3 aim to develop theoretical and numerical tools for robot modeling. Data generated by WP4 will be related to the development and characterization of stimuli-responsive DNA-based hydrogels that exhibit controlled stiffness functions, shape-memory, and self-healing properties. The aforementioned data will be used in WP5 in order to develop an Annelid-inspired soft modular robot featured by shape morphing and responsiveness to stimuli. Selected data will be used for WP6 in order to investigate potential applications and exploitation opportunities of the robot.

In the present document, the term 'data' refers to the following four main categories of information that will be used and/or produced during the project. These are:

1. **Biological Data:** as a result of data collection through the processes as described in the WP2. This data category provides the solid biological background for WP3, WP4 and WP5, by using Annelida Phylum and its evolutionary patterns as a model.
2. **Technical Data:** all data related to WP3, WP4 and WP5 and in particular the processes of Annelid shape-morphing modelling, stimuli-responsive DNA-based hydrogels design and characterization, and finally robot morphing. This category is considered more technical and should be treated separately.
3. **Patent Data:** are those related to WP6 which is dedicated to evaluating the capabilities of the robot in real scenarios in a selected area of application.
4. **Dissemination Data:** refers to the release of information obtained through the MAPWORMS project through social media and its official website, as well as the scientific publications referring to the procedures and/or the results of the research conducted.

Table 1 presents a summary of the research domains and the indicative data, software, and data files that are expected to be used and produced accordingly by the participating partners of the MAPWORMS project. Most of the information provided comes from the answers given by the MAPWORMS partners when replying to the MAPWORMS Data Management Questionnaire (see Annex II), which was based on the questions of the Horizon 2020 FAIR Data Management Plan (DMP) Template ^[1]. This Questionnaire was sent to each participating partner on May 20th, along with instructions, in order to collect information on the data they are going to collect and/or produce during the project and on potential preferences for handling their data.

In particular, **CoNISMa** is going to organize seasonal sampling campaigns. Among the collected specimens, a part will be stored for micro-CT analysis carried out by HCMR, a part will be used for integrated morphological/molecular taxonomic analysis, and a part will be maintained alive in the aquarium facilities of CoNISMa Unit at the University of Salento for rearing experiments. From the aforementioned activities, biological data will be generated (e.g., images, videos, DNA sequences, taxonomical data). Biological data (e.g., 3D images,

videos) related to the Annelids morphology, will be also generated by **HCMR** using the micro-CT technology. Regarding **SSSA**, technical data are expected to be generated (e.g., codes). Those data are strictly connected to the used hardware and specifically for the MAPWORMS project, dedicated systems (gel or characterization setups) will be created. In parallel, technical data in the form of datasheets will be generated by **VEXLUM**, during the process of characterization of the laser systems. **HUJI** will also generate technical data for the synthesis and characterization of stimuli-responsive hydrogels. Finally, data that **ACMIT** is going to generate are related to the evaluation of the project results with respect to identified medical applications at the project's end. Evaluation will take place with tailored anatomical models (phantoms) and the format of this kind of generated data is not defined yet.

Concerning the reusing of any existing data, **CoNISMa** will examine already published literature about annelids along the Salento peninsula to mine historical distributional data. Furthermore, in case of molecular analyses and phylogenetic reconstructions, sequences deposited in online repositories will be used to compare with the newly obtained ones. **HCMR** will examine the protocols and methods of annelids micro-CT scans created by the HCMR imaging laboratory, in order to guide the development of the new micro-CT methods for the MAPWORMS project. The new micro-CT scans will be uploaded to the micro-CTvlab (<https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/>) a web-based virtual laboratory for micro-CT scans of various specimens. For **SSSA** and **VEXLUM**, no existing data will be used as the data are strictly connected to the used hardware and laser systems, accordingly. **HUJI** will apply past accomplishments of the laboratory to design the hydrogels. The pre-existing methods will guide the development of new hydrogel materials. For **ACMIT**, depending on material development and the identified clinical application, existing anatomical data may be used for the generation of the test models.

The expected size of the MAPWORMS data varies, from few MB (e.g., distributional data) to several GB (e.g., micro-CT datasets). As it concerns data utility, researchers from several disciplines will be interested. Furthermore, distributional data derived by **CoNISMa** will give updated biodiversity checklists of annelids in Italian Seas for the Scientific Committee for the Fauna of Italy and for Marine Protected Areas (e.g., Marine Protected Area of Porto Cesareo, Marine Protected Area of Torre Guaceto) and the Apulia Region as required by Italian and European Directives. Molecular data will be useful for building DNA barcode libraries for environmental DNA metabarcoding purposes. Morphological and behavioural data will be useful for MAPWORMS researchers for the development of the annelids modelling. All the aforementioned data will be also useful for annelids taxonomists and ecologists outside the consortium. Despite the taxonomical and ecological interest, the micro-CT data can be used by academics and students for educational purposes, artists and animators for artistic purposes or experts in micro-CT technology for the investigation of digitization protocols and methods. Data derived by **HUJI** will be of broad interest in diverse scientific disciplines, including drug-delivery, sensing, actuating, materials science, and

nanoparticles. Developers of medical technology may be also interested in the MAPWORMS data for medical purposes.

Table 1 The research domains and the indicative data formats and data files that are expected to be produced by the participating partners of the MAPWORMS project.

Partner Contribution	Data Category	Data type	Research domain(s)	Data standards/ vocabularies and softwares/ tools used	Data file types
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional/ Georeferenced data	e.g., biogeographic research, traits, taxonomy	Darwin Core standards, OBIS-ENV-DATA IPT (integrated publishing tool) (open source)	csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx; .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods; .xml; .rff; .txt; .html; .doc; .docx; JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg), TIFF (.tif, .tiff)
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Genomic data	DNA sequencing	M2B3 Reporting Standard Read data: general (CRAM, BAM, Fastq) and platform specific (SFF, PacBio, Oxford Nanopore, CompleteGenomics) Assembled and annotated sequence data: flat file format (FASTA, XML), Multiple Sequence Alignment (MSA) formats	csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx; .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods; SPSS, Stata, Sas, DDI XML, .sav; .dta; xml; .rff; .txt; .html; .doc; .docx; .fas
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Morphological data	e.g., measurements, pictures, drawings	Darwin Core standards IPT (open source)	csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx; .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods; JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg), TIFF (.tif, .tiff),
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Behavioral data	e.g., videos, footages, ethograms		csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx; .txt; doc; .docx; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods; MPEG-4 (.mp4), motion JPEG 2000 (.mj2)), AVI (.avi)
HCMR	Biological Data	Micro CT data	e.g. Micro CT images, digital images, videos, 3D analysis	micro-CTvlab, Slice-Drop (open source) CTAn, CTVox, nRecon (commercial), Drishti (open source)	JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg), TIFF (.tif, .tiff), PNG (.png); MPEG-4 (.mp4), AVI (.avi); csv; .xls; .xlsx; .txt

SSSA, VEXLUM	Technical Data	Modelling data	e.g., numbers, codes, software, mechanical simulations, images, datasheets	MATLAB (academic version), Arduino (open source) LabView (for a fee), CAD software (academic version), COMSOL (for a fee), Repetier-Host (open source)	csv; xls; xlsx; txt; m files; mph files; stl files; eps files; svg files; JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg); pdf
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental data	synthesis and characterisation of stimuli-responsive hydrogels	Origin software	xls; xlsx; JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg), TIFF (.tif, .tiff), PNG (.png); .opj, .opju
SSSA, VEXLUM	Technical Data	Morphing data	e.g., numbers, codes, software, mechanical simulations, images, datasheets	MATLAB (academic version), Arduino (open source) LabView (for a fee), CAD software (academic version), COMSOL (for a fee), Repetier-Host (open source)	csv; xls; xlsx; txt; m files; mph files; stl files; eps files; svg files; JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg); pdf
ACMIT	Patent Data		anatomical models (phantoms)	medical ontologies, such as SNOMED CT or OntoSPM 3D Slicer (open source)	not defined yet
All	Dissemination Data		e.g., presentation, article, etc.	D1.2_project handbook, project Grant Agreement	JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg), TIFF (.tif, .tiff), PNG (.png); txt; .doc; .docx; pdf; html; MPEG-4 (.mp4), AVI (.avi)

2.1 BIOLOGICAL DATA

A crucial first step for the successful output of the MAPWORMS project is related to the taxonomy, behavior, and ecology of Annelida. A dedicated WP, in particular the Work Package WP2 – Ecological, taxonomical and morphological studies for selected species of marine Annelida aims to provide a solid biological background for WP3, WP4 and WP5. Specifically, CoNISMa and HCMR will perform behavioral, ecological, taxonomical, morphological, and anatomical studies aimed at characterizing the identity, ecological and biological traits of Annelida species.

The results of this WP will be the generation of five different types of data which belong to the general category of Biological Data (Table 1):

a. Distributional/ georeferenced data

- b. Genomic data
- c. Morphological data
- d. Behavioral data
- e. Micro CT data

For distributional / georeferenced data, CoNISMa will submit metadata and data from the sampling campaigns to OBIS and in particular to its dedicated node for the Mediterranean Region, which is MedOBIS (<http://medobis.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/>). MedOBIS includes data for the Mediterranean Sea from a wide range of references and time periods and it is encompassed within the framework of OBIS Nodes. It is hosted by the Institute of Marine Biology, Biotechnology and Aquaculture (IMBBC, <https://imbbsc.hcmr.gr/>) of the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR, <https://www.hcmr.gr/en/>). Since the EMODNET (<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en>) and the LifeWatchGreece (<https://www.lifewatchgreece.eu/>) projects, the MedOBIS started operating as a Tier 2 Node. The main principle of MedOBIS is the contribution to science with FAIR and OPEN data. All the data are published through an Integrated Publishing Toolkit (IPT), <http://ipt.medobis.eu/>, harvested by OBIS. The IPT provides the ability to assign DOIs to datasets by using a DataCite account, creating a data repository. The IPT is an open-source software tool, freely available by the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) network.

For distributional/ georeferenced data, a metadata template will accompany every sampling event, in order to collect as much information as possible. This metadata template is presented in Annex III. Regarding data, these will be sent to the MedOBIS Data Management Team in HCMR to be standardized, quality controlled and finally uploaded-published to the MedOBIS Repository, under CC-BY License.

It is worth mentioning that published literature about annelids along the Salento peninsula will be thoroughly examined in order to collect historical distributional data for annelid species. The data derived from this process will be cited and a list of proposed literature will be created. The purpose of this list is to identify interesting and valuable historical datasets that could be digitized and published at a later stage.

Regarding genomic data, the potential repositories that could be used are presented in Annex IV. Most common are ENA and GenBank, but also Barcode of Life Data System (BOLD) is considered suitable. BOLD is an online workbench and database that supports the assembly and use of DNA barcode data. As far as metadata is concerned, according to ENA there is a minimum amount of information required during ENA sample registration and all samples must conform to a defined checklist of expected metadata values. The most suitable checklist for sample registration depends on the type of the sample, which is available online at <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/checklists>.

In case of molecular analyses and phylogenetic reconstructions, sequences deposited in online repositories will be used to compare the newly obtained ones. The material used will be properly cited.

Data regarding annelid morphology, such as measurements, pictures and drawings belong to morphological data. Annelid measurements can be standardized and submitted to MedOBIS, following the same procedure as distributional/ georeferenced data. Whenever possible, there will be a link in the MedOBIS Repository to connect distributional/ georeferenced data with the related morphological data, through the OBIS-ENV data format. This format is based on the Darwin Core Archive (DwC-A, <https://dwc.tdwg.org/>) standard for biodiversity and aims to capture all measurements related to habitat features, such as physical and chemical variables of the environment, and biotic measurements (such as body size, abundance, biomass, etc). For those morphological data that cannot be deposited in MedOBIS then the option of Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) is proposed.

As far as it concerns behavioral data, these refer to annelid behavior (footages, video formats, ethograms etc). These data types may be considered as sensitive for patenting purposes and thus should be treated with care and released only after proper authorization by the IM and the IMB.

Finally, for micro-CT data, HCMR will create micro-CT datasets using the Skyscan 1172 micro-CT in order to visualize the morphological and anatomical characteristics of the specimens provided by CoNISMa. These data will be used to analyze the exterior and interior characteristics of each sample in 3D. All datasets, along with their metadata, will be stored and uploaded in the Micro-CT virtual laboratory (<https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/>). This virtual lab offers to the user a collection of virtual 3D specimens which are annotated with metadata and can be interactively displayed and retrieved through a web-based application [2]. MicroCTvlab has also an API (Application Programming Interface) in order to allow the user to get information on various microCT data scans, species information and metadata related to the microCT dataset scans.

All the aforementioned data and in particular distributional/ georeferenced, genomic, morphological and micro-CT data will be openly available to interested users after an embargo period, which will be estimated at a later stage, mainly depending on the publications foreseen by the participating partners. All protocols used for these data types will be clearly described in the selected repositories and publications. Protocols can also be published in protocols.io (<https://www.protocols.io/>). However, data that can be characterized sensitive due to their use in patenting (WP6), e.g., behavioral data, needs to be handled according to the MAPWORMS Internal Committee.

2.2 TECHNICAL DATA

Apart from Biological Data presented in the previous section, and referred to WP2 activities, Technical data will also be part of the MAPWORMS project. Technical data consist of three different types of data (Table 1), which are:

- a. Modelling data
- b. Experimental data
- c. Morphing data

Modelling data, such as codes, software, mechanical simulations, and images are expected to be produced according to WP3, which aims at developing theoretical and numerical tools to model the shape and shape history of thin sheets driven by modulation of internal stresses and stiffness (algorithmic morphing), inspired by the plasticity of marine Annelida, and exploiting the use of stimuli-responsive shape-memory hydrogels with controllable stiffness.

Modelling data are coming from: dedicated characterization/design process (i.e., mechanical/visual characterization through i) Instron machine, ii) load cells, iii) Hyrox); software for realization process through specific machines (soft materials 3D printer, laser cutter); simulation software; CAD design. Data are strictly connected to the used hardware and in the specific project dedicated systems (gel or characterization set ups) will be created. The tools that can be used in order to access these types of data come mainly with a fee (MATLAB, LabVIEW, CAD software, COMSOL), but there are some open-source software such as Arduino and Repetier-Host. Modelling data would be available through open access publications, as well as through an open access repository such as GitHub and Zenodo (Annex IV).

WP4 deals with Experimental data, including the synthesis and characterization of stimuli-responsive hydrogels. Past accomplishments and experience of HUJI laboratory will be applied to design the hydrogels. The pre-existing methods will guide the development of the new hydrogel materials. These data will be well described through publications envisaged. Experimental data can be stored in Zenodo, as it is shown in Annex IV.

In WP5, SSSA will evaluate responsivity to stimulation gradients in order to optimally mimic biological organism reaction to the environment, thus implementing real morphing adapting machines instead of traditional bi-stable systems. Robot ability to burrow and self-heal its body will also be tested in order to reach different research fields, e.g., environmental application. These data are considered as Morphing data of this project. Morphing data can be stored in Zenodo (Annex IV).

It is worth mentioning that technical data will request a specified embargo period required for patenting, but in the framework of FAIR principles, this period will be reduced as much as possible.

2.3 PATENT DATA

According to WP6, patent data are related to several robots testing towards application case studies and exploitation activities. Data that ACMIT will generate are related to the evaluation of the project results with respect to identified medical applications at project end, while existing anatomical data may also be used to generate the test models.

Patent data will be made available to an extent that allows other interested groups to execute the same tests with their (different) technology. Data related to the technology of prototypes for selected medical applications will be published only after IP protection, e.g., by patent application.

In this framework, an IM and an IMB are appointed for strengthening the IP management. IM and IMB will follow-up the intellectual property protection and actions to support the commercialization of MAPWORMS results. Every 9 months, IMB members summarize the status of exploitation efforts and identify actions in order to expand exploitation opportunities. Among their main tasks are to negotiate and draft license agreements.

2.4 DISSEMINATION DATA

Dissemination data are referring to any information obtained during the MAPWORMS project through social media and its official website and the scientific publications. According to the D1.2 (MAPWORMS_D1.2_project handbook_v5_20220729), when results (e.g., presentation, article, etc.) which were obtained within a WP, are intended to be published by a partner, the WP leader and the IM have to be informed. Furthermore, the Article 17 in the MAPWORMS Grant Agreement mentions that *"a beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate. Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests."*

3 FAIR DATA

MAPWORMS supports the concept of FAIR data (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable) and for this reason invests towards offering its research data as FAIR data.

Annex IV lists some potential (European and non-European) data repositories for redistribution for the thematic data types generated within MAPWORMS. It is noted, that

apart from the patent data, also the data regarding annelid behavior (footages, ethograms, video formats, etc.) might be considered as sensitive for patenting purposes and could be available after proper authorization by the MAPWORMS Internal Committee.

Finally, the used protocols will be described in detail in the selected repositories and in publications in order to increase visibility and reproducibility for any interested users.

3.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

In order to ensure the findability of all produced data by the MAPWORMS project, the following four principles (F1-F4) are supported in this DMP according to the FAIR guide ^[3]:

F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier: all repositories proposed in the Annex IV are using globally unique and persistent identifiers (Digital Object Identifier - DOI) in order to remove ambiguity. An exception is the micro-CTvlab which does not assign DOIs. However, this repository is hosted at the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research which keeps it active over time - through its Network Operations Center (NOC). Furthermore, each dataset uploaded in the micro-CTvlab has been assigned with a unique identifier resulting in a unique URL for each dataset.

F2. Data are described with rich metadata: MAPWORMS project datasets will be described with rich metadata (descriptive information about the data). All partners are encouraged to be generous and extensive when providing metadata information. The concept is that even if the data are not available, at least they are described by rich metadata.

The proposed repositories in Annex IV, have mandatory metadata fields that need to be filled. For example, Zenodo, which will be used as a repository for several types of datasets, has a standard metadata catalogue which will guide the partners for the appropriate metadata fields.

According to the Article 17 of the MAPWORMS grant agreement, metadata of the deposited publications should be licensed under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or equivalent, and provide information at least about the following:

- a. publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue)
- b. Horizon Europe funding
- c. grant project, name, acronym and number
- d. licensing terms
- e. persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant.
- f. persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication (where applicable)

In the case of metadata of deposited data, these must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded) in accordance with Article 17. Furthermore, these metadata should provide information at least about the following:

- a) datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo)
- b) Horizon Europe funding
- c) grant project name, acronym and number
- d) licensing terms
- e) persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant
- f) persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs (where applicable)

F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe:

metadata and the dataset they describe are usually separate files, thus the association between a metadata file and the dataset should be made explicit by mentioning the dataset globally unique and persistent identifier in the metadata.

F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource: datasets will be uploaded in well-known repositories (see ANNEX IV).

Naming conventions are very important as consistent naming increases the findability of the project data. The D1.2 (MAPWORMS_D1.2_project handbook_v5_20220729) has set up the rules for the naming convention of the work package and deliverable reports (Table 2). Datasets names should also be consistent as it is indicated in the following Table 2. Version numbers will be clear in each uploaded dataset. Each partner will be responsible to upload the updated versions of their datasets with the appropriate naming convention and the appropriate version number. Relative keywords should also be provided based on the naming conventions and the metadata.

Table 2 MAPWORMS naming conventions

TYPE OF DOCUMENT	NAME OF THE FILE
Work package report or other project	MAPWORMS_WP[xx]_[kindofreport]_[shorttitle]_rev[xx]_yyyymmdd
Deliverable report	MAPWORMS_D[xx]_[shorttitle]_rev[xx]_yyyymmdd

Data files	MAPWORMS_PartnerName_[shorttitle]_version number[xx]_yyyymmdd
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3.2 MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

To ensure the accessibility of all produced data by the MAPWORMS project, the following two principles (A1-A2) are supported in this DMP according to the FAIR guide ^[3]:

A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communication protocol: Most partners will use http(s) or ftp. A well-organized documentation system and a fully mechanized protocol will ensure freely accessible data. Sensitive data will be guaranteed as FAIR by providing contact details of the data responsible. These details will be explicitly included in the metadata.

A2. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available: This DMP targets to be connected with well-known and well-maintained repositories. Nevertheless, in cases of data unavailability, it is crucial to be able to trace people, institutions or publications associated with the original research. Therefore, this DMP emphasizes the necessity of Metadata availability.

In general, MAPWORMS project supports, where possible, an Open Access Strategy based on the Guidelines about the rules on Open Access to Scientific publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020 (Figure 3).

Following the aforementioned guidelines, here are the subsequent options for the scientific publications:

- a) Self-archiving/ “green” open access, in which the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript can be deposited in an online repository before, at the same time or after the publication. In some cases, open access can be granted after an embargo period.
- b) Open access publishing/ “gold” open access, in which the articles will be immediately published as open access with no publication costs for the subscribers. The university/research institute/agency funding the research, covers the publication costs. In other cases, the costs of open access publishing are covered by subsidies or other funding models.

MAPWORMS project aims to publish the project results as “gold” open access in order to increase the accessibility of the obtained results. When the “gold” open access publishing is not applicable (e.g., conference proceedings or abstract), the “green” open access will be adopted where authors can make pre-prints available to the wider community.

Figure 3 Open access strategy for the access and reuse of research data. Modified image from [4]

The access and use of research data, and in particular those related to the project results patenting (WP6), will be compiled into a protectable form based on the Intellectual Property (IP) protection guided by the Exploitation Plan. MAPWORMS will continuously monitor the project results in order to define the correct strategy for data sharing throughout the project duration. The program will maintain balance between the IP and Open access strategies of the data through constant communication with the IM, the IMB and the DM.

It is proposed that data related to the patenting can be published after an embargo period, once a patent has been filed.

MAPWORMS data can be explored using various software tools. Most of these data will be provided in formats that can be accessed and used through open-source software. Relative documentation and links about the software needed will be available through open access repositories.

According to the D1.2 (MAPWORMS_D1.2_project handbook_v5_20220729), five types of documents will be produced according to their dissemination and confidentiality level:

- PU – Public, fully open, e.g., web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)
- SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

3.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

In order to make the MAPWORMS data interoperable the following three principles (I1-I3) are supported in this DMP according to the FAIR guide ^[3]:

I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. For example, LifeWatchGreece Infrastructure provides to interested users a Data Service, which is mapped to the semantic model of the LWI and the data is transformed to LWI format before it is stored to the Infrastructure.

I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles. MAPWORMS partners should use controlled vocabularies, such as Darwin Core Standards, Marine Regions, where possible, to describe their datasets. These vocabularies should use globally unique and persistent identifiers (e.g., links).

I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data. In this case, any partner should specify if any dataset is built on another dataset or additional datasets/ information are needed for data description. For this reason, MAPWORMS partners should add any relative links between the different datasets.

In this context, all datasets need to be properly cited (i.e., including their globally unique and persistent identifiers), and use controlled vocabularies and ontologies, such as Darwin Core standards for distributional data. The Darwin Core standard includes a glossary of terms intended to facilitate the sharing of information about biological diversity by providing identifiers, labels, and definitions.

Other examples of controlled vocabularies and ontologies, are: a) the WoRMS taxonomic mapping (<https://www.marinespecies.org/index.php>), which is an authoritative classification and catalogue of marine species names maintained at the Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ); and b) the Marine Regions application (<https://www.marineregions.org/>), which is a standard list of marine georeferenced place names and areas.

3.4 INCREASE DATA RE-USE (THROUGH CLARIFYING LICENCES)

In order to optimize the reuse of the produced data by the MAPWORMS project from any interested user, the following principle (R1) is supported in this DMP according to the FAIR guide ^[3]:

R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes: each data owner should provide rich metadata which describe all the aspects of the data generation (e.g., experimental protocols followed, species used, search keywords etc.)

Furthermore, in order to increase the discoverability of the data, a clear licensing status is important for the users and the machines. For this reason, MAPWORMS DMP supports the Creative Commons License. There are several types of Creative Commons licenses which differ regarding the terms of data distribution.

For MAPWORMS metadata the proposed license would be Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC0). CC0 allows the users to freely build upon, enhance and reuse the MAPWORMS metadata without restriction under copyright or database law. For further details see Chapter 3.1.

For MAPWORMS data, the options would be: a) CC BY, which allows the reuse of data (and for commercial use) with the appropriate credit; b) CC BY-NC, which allows the reuse of data (not for commercial use) with the appropriate credit; and c) CC BY-SA, which allows the reuse of data (and for commercial use) with the appropriate credit and the modified data should be licensed under identical terms.

MAPWORMS data will be openly available for re-use to interested users after an embargo period, which will be estimated at a later stage, mainly depending on the publications foreseen by the participating partners and when the patent has been filed.

To stimulate discovery and potential re-use of the metadata and data, MAPWORMS will maximally exploit existing data flow pathways to share data through well-known European e-infrastructures, such as EMODnet and LifeWatch and global initiatives like OBIS and GBIF.

4 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Data management is included in WP1. Ms Dimitra Mavraki was appointed as a Data Manager (DM) for the Data Management Plan (DMP) handling during the MAPWORMS kickoff meeting, on the 13th of May 2022, in Pisa. Ms Dimitra Mavraki is an Environmental Scientist with post-graduate studies on Hydrology and Environmental Management of Water Resources. She has been working as Data Manager at the HCMR, since 2013. She is specialized in marine data collection and digitization, quality control and standardization of both new and historical data, FAIR Principles to marine (meta)data, open access E-infrastructures and Repositories. She has 15 relevant publications and in 2019 she was a Grant winner as an expert European Researcher & Scientist working with data to attend the 14th Research Data Alliance Plenary meeting, in Helsinki, under the theme "Data Makes the Difference". The role of DM is to work closely with each partner in order to guide on how to make MAPWORMS data FAIR. Besides the management of produced data, mainly

allocated by HCMR, all the partners have allocated a dedicated budget for handling and disseminating their data.

During the project, MAPWORMS data are going to be linked to the key European integrating data infrastructures and repositories (EMODnet, MedOBIS, GenBank, Zenodo, MicroCT-vlab) which provide long-term preservation of the data. Further details about the selected repositories can be found in Annex IV.

5 DATA SECURITY

MAPWORMS website (<https://www.mapworms.eu/>) is hosted on the Aruba provider (<https://www.aruba.it/>) which adopts the following protection measures:

- *Anti-DDoS protection.* The DDoS attack are fought by analyzing incoming data, detecting abnormal traffic and, where possible, blocking potentially dangerous packages.
- *Firewalls and WAFs.* Servers' firewalls protect machines' access ports from unauthorized external connections.
- *IDS systems.* Thanks to Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS), the website is constantly monitored from potentially harmful calls in order to intervene with appropriate precautionary blocking measures.
- *Blocking malicious IPs.* Constant monitoring of the main blacklists permits to pre-emptively block any attempts to access your site from any of the reported IP addresses.

Regarding data security and website integrity, these backups are made:

- the provider automatically makes a daily and a weekly backup hosted in the space used for the website and accessible only by ftp;
- a manual backup is performed by the SSSA team every month and stored on a device disconnected from the network.

As reported in the D1.1 (MAPWORMS_D1.1_Website and Project LOGO_V4), MAPWORMS website is also exploitable as a gateway to a private repository platform for the Consortium and only available to registered partners. To protect the registered users' accounts and data from unauthorized access all users must systematically change their login password every 90 days.

Only the SSSA team can access the website storage area to upload reports, results data etc. This private area of the website does not allow for the modification of documents but only the possibility to upload (only by the SSSA team) and download (by the other registered users) of these documents.

The MAPWORMS project will work in collaboration with the major ocean Data Research Infrastructures, which have the mandate for long-term data curation and preservation, such as EMODnet, and LifeWatch ERIC. Zenodo is also a safe certified repository as data are stored in CERN'S Data Centre and it is built and operated by CERN and

OpenAIRE. Furthermore, the DM is going to create a dedicated MAPWORMS community in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/>) which will increase the data curation through the acceptance or rejection of data input in the community collection. MAPWORMS results are recommended to be linked with the MAPWORMS Zenodo community. Details about the selected repositories can be found in ANNEX IV.

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

All ethical aspects of this project are covered in the Ethics Self-Assessment section (pages 21-22) in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Based on the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR- <https://gdpr.eu/>), project partners are responsible for the handling of personal data involved in their activities. MAPWORMS project will not transfer personal data to any other entities

7 OTHER ISSUES

Nothing to report

8 REFERENCES

- [1] Horizon 2020 FAIR Data Management Plan (DMP) Template. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-datamanagement/data-management_en.htm
- [2] Keklikoglou K, Faulwetter S, Chatzinikolaou E, Michalakis N, Filiopoulou I, Minadakis N, et al. (2016) Micro-CTlab: A web based virtual gallery of biological specimens using X-ray microtomography (micro-CT). Biodiversity Data Journal 4: e8740. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.4.e8740>
- [3] Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., et al. (2016) The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Scientific Data 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- [4] Horizon 2020 Online Manual. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/open-access_en.htm

ANNEX I ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meaning
ACMIT	Austrian Center for Medical Innovation and Technology

CoNISMA	Consorzio Nazionale Interuniversitario per le Scienze del Mare
DM	Data Manager
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EMODNET	European Marine Observation and Data Network
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
HCMR	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research
HUJI	Hebrew University of Jerusalem
IM	Innovation Manager
IMB	Innovation Management Board
IP	Intellectual Property
IPT	Integrated Publishing Toolkit
MedOBIS	Mediterranean Ocean Biogeographic Information System
OBIS	Ocean Biogeographic Information System
SSSA	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies
VEXLUM	Vexlum Ltd
WORMS	World Register of Marine Species
WP	Work Package

MAPWORMS Data Management Questionnaire

Please provide your answers to the following questions considering your Institute/ Organization and the data or/and software which you will create or use during the project life.

For any questions you may have please contact Mrs. Dimitra MAVRAKI, dmavraki@hcmr.gr.

Send us your answers at dmavraki@hcmr.gr and keklikoglou@hcmr.gr by June 24th.

(Please give your answers in detail)

1. Data Summary

What types and formats of data are you going to generate/collect throughout the project?

Will you re-use any existing data and how?

What is the origin of your data?

What is the expected size of the data?

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

2. FAIR data

Will you keep metadata describing your data? What type of metadata (description, persons involved, protocols etc.)?

Your produced or used data in the project will be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

How will your data be made accessible (e.g., by deposition in a repository, which)?

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

2.3. Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

How you want your data to be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Are you satisfied with CC-BY?

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Are data quality assurance processes described?

Metadata Format for submitted datasets

* *blue*: obligatory metadata field

* *white*: optional metadata field

Dataset title (= A descriptive title is necessary)	
Dataset citation (= Used to cite the dataset in future publications)	
Persons involved (= Define the persons involved and their specific role (indicate contact person))	
Abstract	
Keywords	
Publications (= Publications based on this dataset)	
Usage/ licence (= Specify if the dataset should be made available for public)	
Release date (=if left empty, dataset will immediately be available to the public, otherwise specify the date of release)	
External links (=Dataset already available elsewhere)	

Geographic coverage <i>(= Specify the location)</i>	
Taxonomic coverage <i>(= Specify the main taxonomic groups)</i>	
Funding and acknowledgments	
Equipment used	
Temporal coverage <i>(=First and last date of sampling)</i>	
Area sampled <i>(=Area sampled by equipment)</i>	
Number of stations	
Coordinates	
Number of Replicates <i>(= Per station/sample)</i>	
Habitat description	
Min/max depth	
Biomass present? <i>specify measuring method</i>	
Count present?	
Environ. variables present?	
Additional remarks	

ANNEX IV POTENTIAL (EUROPEAN AND NON-EUROPEAN) DATA REPOSITORIES FOR REDISTRIBUTION OF THE DATA TYPES WITHIN MAPWORMS PROJECT

Thematic data type category	Research domains	Potential data repositories for redistribution	URLs	Comments
Biodiversity data	e.g. biogeographic research, traits, taxonomy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - European Ocean Biogeographic Information System (EurOBIS) - Mediterranean Ocean Biogeographic Information System (MedOBIS) - Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) - Biology Portal of the European Marine Observation and Data Network 	<p>http://www.eurobis.org/</p> <p>https://obis.org/node/1ad35eb9-c615-4733-864a-b585aebcfb70</p> <p>https://www.gbif.org/</p> <p>http://www.emodnet.eu/biology</p>	<p>Data availability to OBIS under the following Creative Commons licenses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CC-0 CC-BY CC-BY-NC CC BY-SA <p>In addition, shared datasets can be identified and cited through digital object identifiers (DOIs).</p>
Genomic data	DNA Sequencing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) - GenBank - BOLD SYSTEMS 	<p>http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena</p> <p>https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/</p> <p>https://www.boldsystems.org/</p>	BOLD shares a tightly integrated data exchange pipeline with NCBI (GenBank) that allows for automatic submission of data to GenBank.
Morphological Data		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Ocean Biogeographic Information System (EurOBIS) Mediterranean Ocean Biogeographic Information System (MedOBIS) Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) Biology Portal of the European Marine Observation and Data Network Zenodo 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - http://www.eurobis.org/ - https://obis.org/node/1ad35eb9-c615-4733-864a-b585aebcfb70 - http://www.gbif.org/ - http://www.emodnet.eu/biology - https://zenodo.org/ 	
Behavioral data		-Zenodo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://zenodo.org/ 	In Zenodo every upload is assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), Regarding license, users must specify it for all publicly available files. Licenses for closed access files may be specified in the description field.
Micro-CT data	e.g. Micro CT images,	-MicroCT vLab	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://microct.por 	This repository is hosted at the Hellenic Centre for Marine

	digital images, videos		tal.lifewatchgreece.eu/	Research which keeps MicroCT vLab active over time through its NOC- Network Operations Center. The content of the microCT vlab is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)
Modelling data	e.g. software, codes	- GitHub - Zenodo	- https://github.com / - https://zenodo.org /	